

Heterodox methods for interpretable and efficient AI (HMIEAI)

Petter^a ERICSON, Adam^a DAHLGREN LINDSTRÖM, Anna^a JONSSON, Silja^b RENOUIJ, Victor^c DE BOER, Ronald^c SIEBES and Andrew^d LENSEN

^a*Department of Computing Science, Umeå University, Sweden*

^b*Department of Information and Computing Sciences, Utrecht University, Netherlands*

^c*Computer Science department, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands*

^d*School of Engineering and Computer Science, Te Herenga Waka—Victoria University of Wellington, Aotearoa-New Zealand*

Foreword

The workshop Heterodox Methods for Interpretable and Efficient Artificial Intelligence (HMIEAI 2022) took place at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam on June 13, 2022. It was organised as part of the First International Conference on Hybrid Human-Artificial Intelligence (HHAI 2022). The workshop was attended by up to 41 participants.

At HMIEAI we discussed architectures where the human involvement in the design and creation of the model and its data ingestion process allows for both more energy-efficient and more interpretable outcomes. Examples of such systems stretch from pure grammatical inference methods and probabilistic programming, where the model (family) is entirely constructed by human hands and only very specific model parameters are learned from data to various types of interpretable neural network approaches where the specific workings of the output system are much less defined a priori. The goal was to spread knowledge about lesser-known approaches to learning from data that use an increased level of human involvement, require less training data, and are tailored to achieve interpretable results in a more efficient way.

Submissions were invited in two forms: short research papers (5-6 pages) detailing new contributions to the aforementioned fields, and (up to) two-page abstracts summarizing previous work, describing applications, introducing original research directions (including ideas where additional collaborators would be useful), or speculative ideas for community critique and feedback. We received nine submissions, seven of which were accepted after being reviewed by two or three PC-members. All seven accepted papers were presented at the workshop and are part of these proceedings. Additionally, two invited speakers held keynote presentations, the abstracts of which are also included.

The day of the workshop was split into a morning and an afternoon session, each following the same pattern: a keynote presentation to start off the session, presentations of the accepted submissions, and a panel discussion. The panels consisted of all the speakers involved in the respective sessions and were led by a moderator. The morning session was commenced with a keynote talk by Ole-Christoffer Granmo on Tsetlin machines,

and Anil Yaman began the afternoon session with a talk on the emergence of collective intelligence. The first panel discussion covered the balance between interpretability and minimality of models as well as how less transparent models have a higher level of data protection in case of sensitive data. The workshop-concluding second panel discussion focused more on the topic of transparency versus accuracy and the potential harm of seemingly innocent models. The possibility of surrounding opaque networks with additional components that ensure reliability and interpretability without any requirements on the neural network was also discussed.

The members of the organizing committee would like to thank all of the presenters and participants who made the workshop a friendly and inspiring event.